

Climate change and rice production in India

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Rice is India's most important cereal in terms of area and production. By about the year 2020, 65% more rice than the amount produced in 1989 will be needed in the world to meet the demands of the expanding human population (IRRI 1989).

Elevated CO₂ in the atmosphere will affect agricultural production by stimulating photosynthesis (Lemon 1993, Cure and Acock 1986) and improving water use efficiency of crops (Goudriaan and van Laar 1976, Sionit et al 1980). Increased CO₂ can also induce changes in climate, resulting in increased global average annual mean surface air temperature (IPCC Report, Houghton et al 1990). Such global warming is likely to affect agricultural production all over the world.

A crop growth simulation model, ORYZA 1 (Kropff et al 1993), was used to study the effect of temperature rise and elevated atmospheric CO₂ concentration on rice yields in India. The model was validated for the current climate conditions.

Effects of several combinations of temperature increases and atmospheric CO₂ concentrations on simulated yields were studied. The model simulated potential production, which is growth with ample nutrient supply and in the absence of damage by pests, diseases, and weeds.

A temperature increase of up to 2°C over the current level only marginally affected the length of the growing season (from 126 to 125 d). Grain yield, however, declined with a temperature increase of 7°C from 8.0 t/ha to 7.1 t/ha. Regarding locations, places such as Patancheru Bijarpur experienced comparatively greater yield decline (up to 20%) while Kapurthala and Madurai were affected only a little by the increase (see table).

An elevated level of atmospheric CO₂ generally led to an increase in the mean simulated potential yield. With the given weather data, the average increase for India was 11, 20, 28, 40, and 48% for 390, 444, 490, 590, and 680 ppm of atmos-

Effect of temperature rise on simulated grain yield (t/ha) of rice at 9 sites, India.

Site	Temperature rise (°C)						Mean
	0.0	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	
Aduthurai	7.94	7.85	7.80	7.70	7.57	7.35	7.70
Bijapur	6.74	6.47	6.32	6.03	5.86	5.93	6.22
Coimbatore	8.66	8.33	8.11	7.81	7.64	7.58	8.02
Cuttack	6.72	6.48	6.31	6.09	5.99	6.07	6.28
Hyderabad	8.91	8.93	8.61	8.30	8.10	8.14	8.50
Kapurthala	9.74	9.54	9.18	9.07	9.03	8.98	9.26
Pattambi	6.29	6.03	5.76	5.38	5.20	5.27	5.66
Madurai	8.64	8.61	8.53	8.37	8.18	7.89	8.37
Patancheru	8.20	7.92	7.62	7.22	6.91	6.72	7.43
Mean	7.99	7.80	7.58	7.33	7.16	7.10	

pheric CO₂, respectively, compared with the current level of 340 ppm.

The combined effect of doubled CO₂ (680 ppm) and temperature increase (4°C) led to an increase of about 2.5 t/ha (see figure) over current rice yields. In locations such as Kapurthala, Cuttack, and Madurai, the combined effect of doubled CO₂ and temperature increase had the beneficial result of offsetting the yield reduction caused by the temperature increase.

Photosynthesis and stomatal conductance in rice as affected by drought stress

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Agricultural activities, including rice production, may contribute to increased levels of greenhouse gases, such as CH₄ and N₂O, that lead to global warming. Methane emission from ricefields could be reduced if improved rice varieties

The Impact of climatic change (680 ppm CO₂ and/or 4°C increases) on rice yield at 9 locations in India.

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having high yield potential under upland or nonflooded conditions are adopted.

Upland rice often experiences drought stress. Even a partial closure of stomata restricts gas exchange considerably and reduces assimilation rate (Dingkuhn et al 1989). For upland or nonflooded irrigated rice, elevated CO₂ may mitigate, in part, the adverse effects of water deficit. The objective of our study was to test rice cultivars of different origins and growth habits to determine varietal differences in rates of photosynthesis and stomatal conductance under upland conditions compared with lowland conditions.

We conducted two field experiments with four rice cultivars grown under

irrigated and rainfed conditions: Dular, a tall upland cultivar from Bangladesh; Sufaida Pak, a tall rainfed lowland cultivar from Pakistan; and Newbonnet and Katy, modern semidwarf irrigated rices from the USA. Irrigated plots were flooded to a depth of 5-10 cm throughout the growing season, and nonirrigated plots were watered only once in mid-July when the drought period exceeded 15 d and plants were severely wilted. Plants received 39 cm of rainfall from seeding to maturity.

In experiment one, three-row plots with 40-cm row and hill spacings were handseeded with 15 single-plant hills per row. Six plants were pulled from the middle of the center rows of the irrigated plots at 40 d after seeding (DAS) to measure root pulling resistance (RPR) as a measure of deep root density (Ekanayake et al 1986; Price et al 1990). We used a LI-6200 photosynthesis system (LiCor, Lincoln, Nebraska, USA) to measure photosynthetic rate (Pn) and stomatal conductance on the second fully opened leaf of five plants from the center row of each plot at 40 DAS. Gas exchange data were taken before noon when plants in dry plots showed mild stress, but the leaves were not rolled yet.

In the second experiment, six-row plots, 4.75 m long, with a 20-cm row

spacing, were drill-seeded with 110 kg seed/ha. Grain yield and other plant characters were observed.

The four cultivars differed in plant height, tiller number, panicle number, growth duration, and RPR values (Table 1). Based on RPR, Dular and Sufaida Pak had larger deep-root systems than Newbonnet and Katy, and Newbonnet had a significantly larger root system than Katy. Significant interactions between cultivars and water regimes in Pn occurred (Table 2).

Dular and Katy had the highest Pn under nonstressed conditions, whereas Newbonnet had the highest under stressed conditions. Stomatal conductance was highest in Katy followed by Newbonnet and Dular under nonstressed conditions (Table 2). In two of our previous experiments, Newbonnet produced higher biomass and grain yields than the other three varieties under drought stress. Although we do not fully understand why, it is possible that Newbonnet can maintain a greater leaf water potential by osmotic adjustment and a greater sink capacity for continued photosynthesis than the other three varieties.

Our study confirms the finding of Fukushima et al (1985) that cultivars differed in photosynthetic efficiency

under drought stress. Rice cultivars possessing better photosynthetic efficiency and larger deep-root systems exist in the germplasm. They can be used as parents for breeding improved upland cultivars that will more efficiently use increased levels of atmospheric CO₂ in photosynthesis and may contribute to reduced CH₄ emissions under upland conditions, thus reducing the degree of potential global warming due to greenhouse gases.

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Table 1. plant height, tillers/m², panicles/m², days to heading, and root-pulling resistance in four rice cultivars. Pine Bluff, Arkansas, USA, 1992.

Cultivar	Plant height (cm)	Tillers/m ² (no.)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Days to heading (d)	Root-pulling resistance (kg)
Dular	120 a ^a	590 b	553 a	71 b	42 a
Katy	97 b	587 b	495 b	91 a	14 c
Newbonnet	95 b	492 c	418 c	90 a	23 b
Sufaida Pak	124 a	622 a	505 b	88 a	39 a
CV (%)	5.1	7.7	7.2	3.1	9.2

^a Means with the same letters in a column are not significantly different at the 0.05 probability level: av of 4 replications.

Table 2. Photosynthetic and stomatal conductance rate of four rice cultivars, Pine Bluff, Arkansas, USA, 1992.

Cultivar	Photosynthetic rate (μmol/m ² per s)		Stomatal conductance (mol/m ² per s)	
	Irrigated	Nonirrigated	Irrigated	Nonirrigated
Dular	22.9 a ^a	15.0 c	3.0 b	1.8
Katy	23.5 a	17.9 b	4.1 a	2.5
Newbonnet	19.9 b	22.4 a	3.2 b	2.4
Sufaida Pak	17.3 c	10.9 d	2.3 c	2.2
CV (%)	20.43		24.11	

^a Means with the same letter in a column are not significantly different at the 0.05 probability level: av of 4 replications.

Impact of global warming on rice production in Egypt

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Egypt has an arid, subtropical climate in which rice is grown as one of several summer crops following winter crops. Rice was introduced in Egypt in the northern delta near the Mediterranean Sea, at the end of the irrigation system, for controlling salinity. If global warming occurs, the major concerns in Egypt would be the impacts on water supply, sea level, and growing season.

Water supply. Egypt receives essentially no rain; the Nile River is the country's only water source. This water originates in the headwaters of the Blue Nile in the highlands of Ethiopia, some 4000 km upstream from Egypt's ricefields. If a change in climate reduces the rainfall in Ethiopia, Egypt's water supply will be reduced, which will affect the area of irrigated land. If Ethiopia